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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1	<p>Lead authors: Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Fabio Benedetti (ETHZ), Hugo Sarmiento (UFSCar), Paula Huber (UFSCar)</p> <p>Contributing authors: Ruby Rose Bader (ETHZ), Dominic Eriksson (ETHZ), Nielja Knecht (ETHZ), Noémy Chénier (ETHZ), Célio Dias Santos Júnior (UFSCar), Clara Arboleda-Baena (UFSCar), Olivier Jaillon (CEA/GENOSCOPE), Paul Frémont (CEA/GENOSCOPE), Fabien Lombard (SU), Lionel Guidi (SU), Florian Ricour (SU/ULiege), Erik Van Sebille (UU), Darshika Manral (UU), Sophie Schmiz (UU), Corentin Clerc (ENS), Gleice Santos (USP), Luigi Maiorano (UNIROMA1), Daniele De Angelis (UNIROMA1), Sam Chaffron (UNantes), Damien Eveillard (UNantes), Linda Amaral-Zettler (NIOZ), Marion Gehlen (CEA), Germain Benard (CEA), Thomas Frölicher (UBern)</p>	AtlantECO-BASE 1	17.05.2023
2	<p>Lead authors: Meike Vogt (ETHZ), Théophile Sanchez (ETHZ), Hugo Sarmiento (UFSCar), Maria Paula Huber (UFSCar), Célio Dias Santos Júnior (UFSCar)</p> <p>Contributing authors: Fabio Benedetti (ETHZ), Clara Arboleda-Baena (UFSCar), Roniel Freitas (UFSCar), Ruby Rose Bader (ETHZ), Dominic Eriksson (ETHZ), Damiano Righetti (ETHZ), Nielja Knecht (ETHZ), Urs Hofmann Elizondo (ETHZ), Alexandre Schickele (ETHZ), Noémy Chénier (ETHZ), Clara Arboleda-Baena (UFSCar), Olivier Jaillon (GENOSCOPE), Margaux Crédeville (GENOSCOPE), Paul Frémont (GENOSCOPE/CEA), Linda Amaral-Zettler (NIOZ), Or Amar (NIOZ), Fabien Lombard (SU), Zoé Mériguet (SU), Lionel Guidi (SU), Florian Ricour (SU/ULiege), Erik Van Sebille (UU), Sophie Schmiz (UU), Darshika Manral (UU), Corentin Clerc (ENS), Gleice Santos (USP), Gian-Song Nguyen (SINTEF), Tonje Heggeset (SINTEF), Luigi Maiorano (UNIROMA1), Daniele De Angelis (UNIROMA1), Samuel Chaffron (UNantes), Damien Eveillard (UNantes), Marion Gehlen (CEA), Germain Benard (CEA), Thomas Frölicher (UBern) Zoé Mériguet (SU), Or Amar (NIOZ)</p>	AtlantECO BASE 2	24.02.2026

2 Executive summary

This deliverable reports on Task 2.2 ‘Assembly of observations about microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon fluxes’. It used protocols established in task 2.1 ‘Definition of common standards for the assembly of spatially explicit data’ to compile, quality-control and grid existing high-quality observations into a knowledge base of observations (D2.1). Data included into AtlantECO-BASE consisted of contributions from the five following data sources and tasks: Task 2.2.1 ‘Microbiome data from traditional microscopy (presence-absence, abundance and biomass)’, Task 2.2.2 ‘Microbiome data from state-of-the-art optical/imaging analysis’, Task 2.2.3 ‘Microbiome and plastisphere data from state-of-the-art genetic analyses’, Task 2.2.4 ‘Nano-, micro and macroplastics data from state-of-the-art sampling methods’, and Task 2.2.5 ‘Carbon flux data from estimated from high resolution bio-optical sensors’. Some additional data contributions from other partners and work packages are also included. A comprehensive list and description of all data sets collected can be found in the Appendix Tables to this document.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

In recent years, the amount of data generated that is targeted at an improved understanding of marine ecosystem structuring has exponentially increased, yet efforts to reconcile this new information with existing historic data have been scarce, even for relatively well-observed ocean basins such as the Atlantic Ocean. However, data collection has been patchy and biased to target locations such as the North Atlantic, with other areas scarcely sampled, or devoid of publicly available data (South Atlantic Ocean). Initial efforts to generate a knowledge base for plankton functional type biomasses have been made at the global scale (MAREDAT, Buitenhuis et al., 2013), but these datasets do not include the data generated during the past decade, nor do they include the wealth of observations made with novel state-of-the-art sampling methods such as optical imaging or genetic methods. More recent efforts have been made to describe global plankton diversity and distribution using presence-absence data (PHYTOBASE; Righetti et al. 2020; ZOOBASE, Benedetti et al. 2021), or semi-quantitative methods (e.g. Continuous Plankton Recorder CPR; Richardson et al., 2006), and there are now first global collections of metagenomic (e.g. Tara Expeditions) and imaging data (Kiko et al. 2022; Drago et al. 2022), plus a wealth of ever-increasing global data repositories (e.g. COPEPOD; O'Brien, 2010), and a range of individual cruises and expeditions that make their data publicly available (e.g., Tara; Pesant et al. 2015).

Here, we aim to bring together and harmonise publicly available geo-referenced data on the marine microbiome and its functions and stressors/pollutants from major data repositories with large-scale expeditions gathered during the past decade, across taxonomic groups and sampling methods to generate global data products (for use in statistical mapping and extrapolation) with a particular emphasis on the Atlantic Ocean (All-Atlantic Microbiome Atlas). We gathered marine microbiome data from traditional (task 2.2.1), imaging (task 2.2.2), and genetic (task 2.2.3) methods, as well as information on ecosystem functioning (carbon fluxes, task 2.2.4) and ecosystem pollutants (plastics, task 2.2.3). Presence-absence, abundance, biomass and diversity data sets are available for use within the project in WP3 (marine ecosystem health and services), WP5 (advances in systems ecology), WP6 (advances in model predictability), comparable with assessments carried out in WP7 (ecosystem change) and WP8 (predictions of and for ecosystem services). Vice versa, we also record a range of output products generated in the other work packages in our collection, such as data on connectivity, plankton networks and a range of additional 'omics resources.

All geo-referenced data are provided as a collection of data csv (AtlantECO-BASE) and gridded netcdf files (AtlantECO-GRID). Data that are either not geo-referenced and/or unsuitable for re-formatting into csv and netcdf formats are retained in their native data formats and recorded as links to published material (section 4.8; AtlantECO-ELSE), and an initial collection of CMIP6 simulations for future projections is also made available for use (section 4.10; AtlantECO-CMIP6).

A set of globally extrapolated gridded data fields has been generated from AtlantECO-BASE using state-of-the-art species distribution modelling (AtlantECO-MAPS; D2.5). All data sets have been made publicly available to partners, sister projects (including BiOceans5D, MissionAtlantic and BlueCloud2026) and the wider science community.

In fact, AtlantECO-BASE has reached an audience far beyond the project, and is being used in a wide range of science projects worldwide, many of which led by early career scientists. Multiple MSc and PhD theses (Schmiz, MSc thesis, 2021, Ricour, PhD thesis, 2023; Li, MSc thesis, 2023, Chénier, MSc thesis 2023; Knecht, MSc thesis, 2022, Poli, MSc thesis, 2023, Berger, MSc thesis, 2025) and papers (e.g., Frémont et al. 2022, Benedetti et al., 2023, 2025; Knecht et al., 2023) have been published based on AtlantECO-BASE and many more works are under review, submitted or in preparation, thus showing that AtlantECO-BASE has proven to be a solid foundation for further important scientific work beyond the end of the project. For example, AtlantECO-BASE has formed the basis for the development of a cloud-based marine ecosystem modelling

pipeline within sister EU HORIZON project BlueCloud2026 (Schickele et al. 2025; Schickele et al., in prep.; Clerc et al., in prep.), and it is part of the historical data collection in sister EU HORIZON project BiOcean5D (BiOcean5D deliverable D1.3).

4 AtlantECO-BASE: Data products

4.1 Data standards, quality control and formatting (task 2.1; lead: ETHZ)

All geo-referenced raw data sets have been formatted as long table using the Darwin Core (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>) standard vocabulary (DwC) for transmitting information about biodiversity, including a standard list of data and meta-data descriptors (data column headers), which makes the data compatible with major international data repositories such as the EMODnet Biology Portal (see <https://www.emodnet-biology.eu/data-infrastructure>), the Global Biodiversity Facility (GBIF) and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS). In line with the convention of these data repositories, all taxonomically annotated microbiome data uses the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) taxonomic classification for reference (<https://www.marinespecies.org/>). Gridded data files have been created in NetCDF format using CF metadata (<https://cfconventions.org/>) for the dissemination on AtlantECO's GeoNode. Each data set generated anew within the framework of AtlantECO by AtlantECO partners is accompanied by a README file that details authors, variable names, sources, metadata included, methodology used to create added value (e.g. biomass conversion from abundance to biomass), as well as references to related scientific publications. Data sets that were generated either by or in collaboration with third parties but serviced to AtlantECO are reported in their original form.

All traditional microbiome data gathered have been taxonomically matched to the WoRMS taxonomic backbone for reference, quality controlled (as detailed in Righetti et al., 2020 for phytoplankton; and Benedetti et al., 2021 for phyto- and zooplankton) and recorded with all meta-data available. Biological records associated with non-marine organisms were discarded. Biological records (presence-absence or abundances) with missing or erroneous spatial coordinates or sampling date (day/month/year) were removed. Biological records missing information about their discrete sampling depth, or sampling depth interval ('MinDepth' and 'MaxDepth'), were also removed. For the datasets synthesising quantitative counts (abundances and biomass records), the records associated with negative or missing abundance/cell concentration values were also considered dubious and therefore discarded. Microbiome/plankton taxa whose scientific name could not be associated with any accepted name (e.g., an accepted AphiaID numeric code from WoRMS) were flagged as such in the 'WoRMS_ID' header. Data quality flags and/or comments inherited from the original data sources were retained (in the 'Note' and 'Flag' headers). All metadata headers were reformatted according to the DwC conventions. Data that were recorded in public long-term data repositories such as OBIS or GBIF have retained their full provenance (e.g., original records' ID and metadata), and all original literature references were given where data could be matched against a peer-reviewed publication. All available absences (i.e., null abundances) were retained, but not all original sources consistently recorded absences (MAREDAT; CPR).

All metagenomic data gathered have been submitted as an AtlantECO Superstudy on EMBL-EBI's MGnify platform (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/super-studies/atlanteco>) and are being processed using MGnify's bioinformatics analysis pipelines (version 5.0). Only georeferenced samples with sampling date and water column depth information were considered. The raw data underwent a quality control and contamination removal process using *bwa-mem* algorithm as described in Mitchell et al. (2020). A subset of metagenomes already analyzed was selected to explore the microbiome functional diversity. The dataset contains only samples from the 0.22-3 μm size fraction. Samples with <10,000 reads were removed and total reads number was normalized to equalize sampling depth. Each data record is accompanied with sample and contextual environmental metadata. All metadata headers were reformatted according to the DwC conventions. Using protein data from 1379 metagenomes, we define **Operational Protein Units (OPUs)** through a sensitive heuristic clustering strategy that captures both known and unknown amino acid sequences, including those associated with "functional dark matter" often missed by traditional analyses.

Protein sequences longer than 35 residues were clustered using MMseqs2's linclust algorithm ($\geq 97.5\%$ identity) via a custom pipeline ([OPUs_pipe](#)). Functional annotation was performed with eggNOG-mapper v2, assigning KEGG Orthology (KO) terms to each protein. OPUs lacking KO annotations were classified as Unknown OPU. Based on their occupancy across sampling basins, OPU were further categorized as Core (present in all basins). The resulting spatial profile and functional annotation are accessible in AtlantECO-BASE. Two complementary datasets were developed to evaluate both functional and taxonomic diversity across **metagenomic samples**. **Functional diversity** is based on an updated version of the dataset presented in Database1, now including additional samples and new diversity indices (Simpson and Chao). For each sample ($n = 1,676$), functional tables containing KEGG Orthology (KO) abundances were downloaded from MGnify and merged into a single matrix. From this table, functional diversity and richness were estimated using the Shannon, Simpson, and Chao indices in the R software environment (vegan package). **Taxonomic diversity** is derived from a newly created database. Taxonomic profiles were generated by running mOTUs on MGnify. For each sample ($n = 1,210$), tables containing mOTUs taxonomic assignments were downloaded and compiled into a single table. Diversity and richness were then calculated from this dataset using the Shannon, Simpson, and Chao indices in R (vegan package).

The metabarcoding dataset for planktonic communities consists of an integration of quality-controlled sequencing data from the Tara Ocean and Malaspina expeditions. The primers used for the V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene were 515FB: GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGTAA and 926R: CCGYCAATTYMTTTRAGTTT (Quince et al., 2011; Parada et al., 2016) and for the V9 region of the 18S rRNA gene were 1389F: 5'-TTGTACACACCGCCC-3' and 1510R: 5'-CCTTCYGCAGTTACCTAC-3' (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2009). Amplicon sequences were processed using the DADA2 pipeline (Callahan et al., 2016; Lee, 2019) to characterize Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) that were used as a proxy of microbial species (Callahan et al., 2017). Each sequencing project was analyzed separately because different runs can have different error profiles following Callahan et al. (2016). The quality of the samples was explored, and the trimming and filtering parameters were chosen according to Callahan *et al.* (2016). After merging the runs, the taxonomic classification was performed using the IDTAXA algorithm implemented in the DECIPHER package for the R programming language (Murali et al., 2018) and the SILVA database (SILVA SSU r138 2019) for 16S rRNA gene primers (Quast et al., 2012) and PR2 database (PR2 v4.13) for 18S rRNA gene primers as a reference (Guillou et al., 2012). Only samples with more than 10,000 reads were analyzed, and we kept ASVs with 50 reads distributed in at least three samples or those that have less than 50 reads distributed in more than three samples.

All metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs) and single-amplified genomes (SAGs) included in the database were pre-compiled from the Ocean Microbiomics Database v.1 (Paoli et al., 2022), comprising expeditions conducted by Tara Oceans, BioGEO TRACES, Hawaiian Ocean Time-series (HOT), Bermuda-Atlantic Time-series Study (BATS), and Malaspina. To ensure the quality of data, we only included genomes with a completeness of at least 90% and contamination below 5%, following the criteria established by Parks et al. (2015, 2017). Additionally, we focused on genomes with fewer than 500 contigs, an N50 of at least 10 Kbp, and tRNAs encoding for at least fifteen different amino acids. We excluded genomes from viral fractions and those lacking depth or size fraction information. After this meticulous process, we worked with 2,215 high-quality genomes, categorised into epipelagic, mesopelagic, and bathypelagic zones for our analyses. By using a pipeline we developed, CaCo (<https://github.com/celiosantosjr/CaCo>), we predicted the carbohydrate substrates based on their enzymes annotated from dbCAN3 (Zheng et al., 2023), and included the information about the estimated number of carbon substrates used per genome and the number of CAZyme protein families found.

All optical imaging data processed within AtlantECO (including Tara Oceans and Tara Pacific) is recorded as images on ECOTAXA (<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr>) with meta-data standards complying with Pesant et al., (2015) and sample registry (<https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.875582>), station registry (<http://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.842237>) and event registry

(<http://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.842227>) located within Pangaea for the Tara Ocean cruise and ongoing similar effort for Tara Pacific (Lombard et al., accepted, 2022, and cited registry therein). All positions, depth and sampled volumes were triple checked against registries and logsheets. Protocols and QC had followed protocols from the Quantitative Imaging Platform of Villefranche (PIQV <https://sites.google.com/view/piqv>, Jalabert et al., 2022). Zooscan, UVP and Flowcam data were segmented after background removal by zooprocess, multiples objects on zooscan were QC and further segmented (<https://sites.google.com/view/piqv/softwares/flowcamzooscan?authuser=0>). Planktoscope data were acquired according to newly established protocols and imported in Ecotaxa (Lombard et al., 2022a; Lombard et al., 2023). All images were annotated to a given taxonomic level (taxonomically matched to the WoRMS taxonomic backbone for reference) by taxonomic expert using an IA assisted method using standard Ecotaxa protocols (Irisson et al., 2022).

All carbon data acquired within AtlantECO have been gathered from published data collections (Underwater Vision Profiler 5 (UVP5) data from <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.924375>, sediment traps data (non-exhaustive) from <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.855600> and Thorium-234 data (non-exhaustive) from <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.809717>). UVP5 data were quality checked following Kiko et al., (2022). Sediment traps and Thorium-234 data were quality checked (geolocalization error, duplicates, range and outlier checks) using all meta-data available. The effort to derive a general relationship to convert particle size distributions (PSD) into estimates of particulate organic carbon (POC) fluxes is ongoing (Ricour et al., PhD thesis, ongoing). Hence, we first provide UVP5 PSD instead of POC flux estimations in this first data release.

All microplastics data were retrieved from the literature and combined with the global collection by Sebille et al., (2015) for small plastics (microplastics mostly < 5 mm in diameter). The description below closely follows that of Schmitz, MSc thesis, (2021; doi:10.5281/zenodo.5338790). Beyond the approximately 11,000 data records already in Van Sebille et al., (2015), new datasets were collected using searches on Google, Google Scholar, Google Dataset Search, and LITTERBASE. This resulted in 648 new data points from 14 data sets with particle sizes ranging from 32 μ m to 25 mm. If plastic particles were sampled by nets, they were trawled mostly at the sea surface with bongo, neuston or manta nets with mesh sizes between 100 μ m and 500 μ m, although the typical mesh size for these trawls is 300 μ m. One data set was collected in a multi-level trawl in the water column. Other samples in the water column were obtained by pumping seawater through a mesh at the bottom of the vessel. Because of contamination concerns, most data sets excluded fibres, except for Brach et al., (2018), Kanhai et al., (2017) and Montoto-Martinez, Hernandez-Brito, and Gelado-Caballero (2018). Although the mesh size of the trawling nets and in the pump filters generally sets a lower limit to the detectable particle size, it is not uncommon that smaller particles end up in the final sample as well, either as aggregates or by clogging the mesh. Different data sets are often given in different units that need to be converted before the data sets can be combined. To this end, data were converted to units of number of particles per km² and total mass per km² using conversion routines following Kukulka et al., (2012), as detailed in section 2.3 of Schmitz, (2021), doi:10.5281/zenodo.5338790.

Where AtlantECO-specific model runs for AtlantECO-MAPS1 (D2.3) were made (e.g. Benedetti et al., (2021)), statistical species distribution models for the extrapolation of geo-referenced data in space and time have been developed in accordance with the model quality protocols developed for the modelling of scarce and biased data (task 2.1), as detailed in Righetti et al., submitted (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.28.530497>), and species distribution models have been documented in agreement with current community standards as documented in Zurell et al., (2020). Outputs of species distribution models and other analysis products that have been developed by external partners to the project, or prior to the project start are recorded as published.

Dataformatting procedure for AtlantECO-BASE1 and AtlantECO-BASE2

This second version of **AtlantECO-BASE** includes new datasets as well as a reformatted version of those from the first release. A **Python script** ([dataset parser repository](#)) has been developed to automate the reformatting process, generate figures, and extract key information from each dataset to produce a README file in PDF format. The parser is designed to work with any tabular dataset, making it applicable beyond AtlantECO. It also allows us to easily add modifications and reformat all the datasets. To process a dataset, it relies on information provided in a YAML configuration file and, when necessary, on an additional Python script to handle formatting tasks not covered by the main parser. All configuration files for AtlantECO datasets, along with the scripts used to generate the figures in this document, are stored in the [AtlantECO parser repository](#).

The new version aligns more closely with the **Darwin Core vocabulary** by applying fuzzy matching to map previous column names to a predefined list of standard terms. Column names that are not included in this list are retained as they are. Column values are validated using the **Pandera** package, which raises warnings when they fail the tests defined in the [check.py script](#). Filenames now follow a consistent naming convention and include the principal author's name for datasets not funded by AtlantECO. All files now use a CSV format and UTF-8 encoding.

The previous version of AtlantECO-BASE remains available in the [legacy folder](#), and the corresponding R scripts used to generate it are stored in a dedicated [repository](#).

4.2 Data access

All data can already be accessed by the project team from a dedicated public transfer folder located at partner ETHZ. Raw data is accessible at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/BASE/>, gridded raw data in netcdf format at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/GRID/>, and fields extrapolated using statistical and machine learning tools at <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/MAPS/>. Published AtlantECO-MAPS are partly hosted by and distributed through AtlantECO's GeoNode (<https://atlanteco-geonode.eu/>) where available until the project end (February 2026), and through SEANOE (<https://www.seanoe.org/>). Data submissions from previous publications are referenced with their original references and data dois, so that all data published in international data repositories can also directly be sourced from the respective original data providers. Service datasets not funded by AtlantECO but provided to the AtlantECO science community in standardized formatting are clearly marked as such. Password protection is enabled for a range of studies that are still in preparation, which will be removed two years after the project ends (April 2028). In the meantime, access can be granted by the data owner, who is indicated in the public readme files for each data submission.

A comprehensive list of all data sets collected for overview can be found in the **Appendix Tables** to this document.

SUMMARY STATISTICS:

Data silo	Data subset	Number of observations*
Traditional	Presence-absence	22,124,209
Traditional	Abundance/Biomass	19,732,919
Omics	Metagenomes	4,042,035
Omics	16S	170,923
Omics	18S	479,344
Imaging	Synthesis products	1,607,197
Imaging	Images	8,183,578
Carbon fluxes	234Th/Sediment traps	15,426
Carbon fluxes	UVP particle sizes	4,698,169
Microplastics	Microplastics concentrations	13,159
Bioprospecting	Enzyme hits	4,011
Service products	Data in multiple data silos	10,963

*: Number of observations counted as numbers of lines in csv files. Please note that this does not necessarily correspond to the number of samples, nor the number of observational stations, as often, multiple biological entities were assessed at each station.

All in all, the 61,081,933 observations cover 519,276 monthly grid points and 1,298,190 annual grid points. i.e. 49% of the ocean surface area, and 8% of the climatological space-time (for years times cells; 12% for month times cells), which shows that temporal bias is more prominent than spatial bias alone.

4.3 Microbiomes data from traditional microscopy (task 2.2.1; lead: ETHZ)

This collection brought together existing observations on the diversity and distribution of phyto- and zooplankton functional types from a range of publicly available resources and AtlantECO target expeditions on presence-absences (including updated versions of PHYTOBASE and ZOOBASE; Righetti et al., 2020; Benedetti et al., 2021), abundances (including observations from MAREDAT; Buitenhuis et al., 2013), the CPR surveys, BODC, COPEPOD, JeDI, KRILLBASE, Malaspina, Tara, among other efforts), and biomasses. Data have been quality controlled according to Benedetti et al., (2021), using the WoRMS' taxonomic classification. Biomasses have been calculated according to community standard protocols, e.g. those used in MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al., 2013) or as described in the relevant readme file and accompanying literature (see Clerc et al., doi:10.5194/bg-20-869-2023; Knecht et al., doi:10.2254/essoar.167283650.05543210/v1; Eriksson et al., in preparation; Chénier et al., in preparation).

All in all, the data collection brought together > 21 million presence-absence and abundance observations, including 5,167,282 presence-absence observations for phytoplankton (1,691 accepted taxonomic names), 16,574,064 presence-absence observations for zooplankton (4,062 accepted taxonomic names), 4,756,047 phytoplankton abundance and biomass observations (1,072 accepted taxonomic names), 15,294,171 zooplankton abundance and biomass observations (1,262 accepted taxonomic names) and 22,461 nitrogen fixer abundance and biomass observations (20 species from 15 genera). These data sets are documented in a range of MSc theses (N. Knecht, MSc thesis, 2022 (pteropods and foraminifera); N. Chénier, MSc thesis, 2022 (dinoflagellates)) and new papers (Benedetti et al., 2021 (phytoplankton and zooplankton); Benedetti et al., 2022 (copepods); Benedetti et al. 2023 (copepods), Benedetti et al. 2025 (copepods); Knecht et al., 2023 (pteropods and foraminifera); Clerc et al., 2023 (salps); Eriksson et al., in review (diazotrophs); Eriksson et al., under review (prokaryotes)). Existing data on diatoms (Leblanc et al., 2012) and coccolithophores (O'Brien et al., 2013) from MAREDAT (Buitenhuis et al., 2013), phytoplankton presence absence data from PHYTOBASE (Righetti et al., 2020) and zooplankton data from ZOOBASE (Benedetti et al., 2021) has been reformatted and delivered in its original form.

Compared to AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1), the final version of AtlantECO-BASE (D2.3) integrates corrections of the previous biomass conversion errors in the copepod biomass data.

A list of all data products can be found in **Tables A 4.3.1 and 4.3.2**.

SUMMARY STATISTICS: Presence-absence observations:

Total number of data sets: 4

Total number of observations: 24,556,001

Fraction of publicly available data sets from global data repositories: 50% (2,725,852 observations; 11% of obs)

Fraction of data sets available by download/upon e-mail request: 50% (21,830,149 observations; 89% of obs.)

SUMMARY STATISTICS: Abundance and biomass observations:

Total number of data sets: 15

Total number of observations: 203,20,251

Fraction of publicly available data sets from global data repositories: 100%

4.4 Microbiomes data from optical/imaging analysis (task 2.2.2; lead: SU)

The AtlantECO-BASE collection of imaging data consists of (a) the integration of new quality-controlled data from historic and AtlantECO flagship cruises (Mission Microbiome, Tara Oceans, Tara Pacific, and 147 other cruises for UVP data), and (b) published synthesis products on particle size distribution and zooplankton community structure and biomass. The former data sets have been integrated with Ecotaxa (<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>; Picheral et al., 2017) and EcoPart (<https://ecopart.obs-vlfr.fr/> for UVP-particles data), which allows an automatic prediction of the taxonomic classification of each single image followed by a manual validation/correction. Full methodological details on data treatment and processing using machine learning are given in Irsson et al. (2022).

Published data were quality-controlled and annotated according to community standards and using standard Ecotaxa protocols (Irsson et al., 2022), see also <https://sites.google.com/view/piqv/piqv-manuals/ecotaxaecopart-manuals?authuser=0>. All new Ecotaxa data is directly integrated with EMODnet Biology, and thus OBIS and GBIF, according to new exchange protocols (Martin-Cabrera et al. 2022; doi:10.3897/biss.6.94196), as developed within the H2020 project JERICO SE in collaboration with EMODnet. The collection includes more than 8.1 million new quality-controlled plankton images from 3 cruises integrated into the Ecotaxa imaging platform (<https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>), from the following projects/studies: Tara Ocean (3.9 million images), Tara Pacific (2.9 million images) and the Flagship cruise from AtlantECO Tara Microbiomes (>1.2 million images, sample analysis on-going) across a range of different imaging instruments and nets. Finally, the data set includes a compilation of UVP JERICO data (74,769 images). Novel imaging data has been documented and interpreted in a range of scientific publications (Drago et al. 2022; Kiko et al. 2022; Mériguet et al. 2022; Lombard et al., in prep.; Brandao et al. 2021; Soviadan et al., 2022), see also the next paragraph below.

Published imaging synthesis products consist of a range of project-associated and or related integrated data products that were kindly provided by institutions and principal investigators outside AtlantECO. Although their work was not funded by AtlantECO, these contributors reformatted and shared their research outputs in recognition of their high relevance to AtlantECO's objectives. Most of these contributions are based on imaging data that have been published in collaboration with AtlantECO partners (Kiko et al. 2022; Soviadan et al., 2022, Brandao et al. 2021). The contributed synthesis datasets include 15,908 observations of zooplankton abundance and community composition from Tara Oceans (Brandao et al. 2021; Soviadan et al., 2022). It also delivered the compilation of 8,805 vertical profiles of particle size and concentration distributions based on a compilation of multiple UVP5 camera systems (Kiko et al. 2022), and 466,872 observations of zooplankton abundances from 3,449 vertical UVP5 profiles (Drago et al. 2022), in the form originally published by their project-external first authors. All such contributions are explicitly identified as *service products* in Table 4.4.2 and flagged as service datasets within the AtlantECO-BASE collection.

Compared to AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1), the final version of AtlantECO-BASE additionally contains 695 georeferenced metaplankton assemblages from Lombard et al. (2024). This dataset has been recorded using 11 complementary imaging platforms, including flow cytometry (FACScalibur, Accuri), Imaging FlowCytobot (IFCB), FlowCam, environmental High-Content Fluorescent Microscopy (eHCFM), ZooScan, and Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP).

The final version of AtlantECO-BASE also adds 25,538 records of plankton and plastic abundances computed from a harmonized collection of 2,335,056 images of surface plankton and particles across the Pacific Ocean and parts of the North Atlantic (Mériguet et al., 2024). This study includes 585 georeferenced plankton samples acquired using two complementary imaging systems: FlowCam (for microplankton, 20–200 µm) and ZooScan (for mesoplankton, >300 µm), alongside manual imaging of plastic debris. Samples were collected using custom-designed high-speed and stationary net systems, including the Dolphin pump-fed Deck-Net,

Bongo nets towed by underwater scooters, and high-speed tow nets (HSN and Manta). This product is presented in a reformatted version consistent with AtlantECO's guidelines.

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.4** for raw images and **Table A 4.4.1** for synthesis products.

SUMMARY STATISTICS:

Synthesis products:

Total number of integrated data sets: 6

Total number of observations: 4,698,169

Fraction of publicly available data sets in global data repositories: 83% (4,696,822 observations; ~100% obs.)

Fraction of data sets available by download/upon e-mail request: 17% (37 stations; > 1% of obs.)

Fraction of data sets currently not available: 0%

Raw images processed and uploaded onto Ecotaxa:

Total number of Ecotaxa projects: 57

Total number of new quality controlled Ecotaxa images: 8,183,578

Fraction of currently publicly viewable validated Ecotaxa projects as recorded below: 43%

(Tara Oceans: 87%, Tara Pacific: 31%, Mission Microbiome: 88%, JERICO: 100%)

4.5 Microbiomes and plastisphere data from molecular analyses (task 2.2.3; lead: UFSCar)

The AtlantECO-BASE collection of genetic data consists of metabarcoding and metagenomics datasets from planktonic communities and plastisphere across different aquatic environments. Publicly available metagenomics data were obtained from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), corresponding to eight expeditions, including Tara Oceans, Malaspina, GO-SHIP, GEOTRACES, and OSD, as well as 16 oceanic cruises. Raw data have been submitted to MGnify and organized under the umbrella of the [‘AtlantECO’ superstudy](#). The raw data analysis is currently being carried out using the last version of MGnify’s pipeline (V5.0). Data have been quality controlled as described in Mitchell et al. (2020). Amplicon data from planktonic communities have been collected from Tara Oceans and Malaspina expeditions. All data has been quality-controlled according to Callahan et al., (2016).

All in all, the compilation brought together 3,597 marine metagenome observations, 428 16S rRNA and 1,405 18S rRNA amplicon observations, 357 16S rRNA plastisphere amplicon observations, and 162 plastisphere metagenomes. The compilation includes: (1) microbial functional diversity (from 451 metagenomes of 0.2-3µm size fraction), (2) counts of representative genes of Nitrogen metabolism (from 451 metagenomes of 0.2-3µm size fraction), (3) taxonomic diversity of prokaryotes (from 428 samples with a total of 13378 ASVs), (4) autotrophic prokaryotes abundances (from 428 samples with a total of 332 ASVs), (5) heterotrophic prokaryotes abundances (from 428 samples with a total of 13046 ASVs), (6) taxonomic diversity and abundance of eukaryotes (from 1405 samples with a total of 9175 ASVs). A subset of the metagenomic data collected in AtlantECO (Tara) has been documented in Frémont et al. (2022), and a new publication that will analyse the full AtlantECO data set is in preparation (Huber et al. in preparation). High-quality metagenome-assembled-genomes (MAGs) results have been documented in Dias Santos Junior et. al. (2025)

Compared to AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1), this final version of AtlantECO-BASE additionally contains functional diversity from 1,676 metagenomes from global ocean, collected in different oceanographic expeditions, targeting the pico-size microbial size-fraction, taxonomic diversity from 1,210 metagenomes from global ocean, collected in different oceanographic expeditions, targeting the pico-size microbial size-fraction, the distribution of 20 Core Operational Protein Units (OPUs), present across all ocean basins, metadata of 2,215 high-quality metagenome-assembled-genomes (MAGs) from samples collected from marine expeditions around the globe, an estimated number of carbon substrates used per each of 2,215MAGs, an estimated number of CAZYme protein families found in each of 2,215MAGs.

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.5**.

SUMMARY STATISTICS:

Total number of data sets: 3

Total number of observations: 2668

Fraction of publicly available data sets from global data repositories: 100% (2668 observations; 100% of obs)
(Tara Oceans: 74.1%, Malaspina 14.6%, OSD 14: 5.2%, bioGEOTRACER: 2.9% Anaconda: 3.1%)

4.5.1 Plastisphere Community from Amaral-Zettler et al. (2015)

Amplicon data from the plastisphere were collected in different environments from the North Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. Data quality was controlled as described in Amaral-Zettler et al. (2015). Raw data is freely available in the ENA repository. This submission consists of a dataset of bacterial communities from plastic samples (Plastisphere) from the North Pacific and North Atlantic subtropical gyres. The bacterial community composition was studied by amplicon sequencing Illumina technology using the V6 hypervariable region of the 16S rRNA gene. The sampling strategy and sample processing are described in Amaral-Zettler et al. (2015). The raw data was submitted in MGnify ([MGYS00001767](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/MGYS00001767)) and analyzed using version 3.0 of the amplicon pipeline.

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.5.1**.

4.6 Carbon flux data from bio-optical sensors (task 2.2.1; lead: SU)

The compilation of particulate organic carbon fluxes results from the compilation of historical data obtained with sediment traps and derived from Thorium-234 deficits for a total of 15,425 observations. These data were QC,d as described above. The Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP5) measures the size distribution of particles in the 0.05 - 26 mm range (27 size classes). 8,728 UVP5 profiles were quality controlled according to Kiko et al. (2022) for a total of 2,083,352 observations. Carbon fluxes were derived from UVP data according to the methodology as detailed in Guidi et al. (2008). In brief mass and settling rates of particles, $m(d)$ and $w(d)$, respectively, are often described as power law functions of their diameter (d) obtained by fitting observed data, $m(d) \times w(d) = Ad^b$. The particles carbon flux can then be estimated using an approximation of the integral of $n(d) \times m(d) \times w(d)$ (n being the number of particles) over a finite number of small logarithmic intervals for diameter d spanning from 250 μ m to 1.5 mm (particles <250 μ m and >1.5 mm are not considered, consistent with the method presented Guidi et al. 2008).

No changes between AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1), and AtlantECO-BASE2 (this deliverable) were made.

SUMMARY STATISTICS:

Total number of data sets: 3

Total number of observations: 4,182,130

Fraction of publicly available data sets from global data repositories: 0% (0 observations; 0% of obs)

Fraction of data sets available by download/upon e-mail request: 100% (4,182,130 observations; 100% of obs.)

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.7**.

4.7 Microplastics data (task 2.2.1; lead: UU)

Microplastics data were obtained from an extensive literature review (Sebillé et al. 2015) which was augmented with data from 16 additional cruises (Schmiz, 2021, MSc thesis). Data include counts of small plastics with a size < 5 mm, which were gathered using a range of nets with varying mesh sizes. All data were converted from numbers and concentrations per volume or area into concentrations per km² using the conversion routines as documented in Kulkera et al. (2012). All in all, the data compilations contain 13,159 small and microplastics observations.

No changes between AtlantECO-BASE1 (D2.1), and AtlantECO-BASE2 (this deliverable) were made.

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.7**.

4.8 Molecular bioprospecting from SINTEF

This table contains a list of 4,013 sequences from seven enzyme families which are of high interest for the stakeholders in the case study 1 (Molecular Bioprospecting) and subtask 2.4.1. The name of the enzyme families as well as the full sequences have been redacted as requested by the stakeholders. The seven enzyme families activities and functions include activity towards DNA/RNA as well as involvement in cellular defence systems. The sequences were sourced from the AtlantECO superstudy in the MGnify database (Richardson et al., 2023). Further selection and characterisation of the candidates will be carried out by the stakeholders jointly with SINTEF in follow-up projects.

This data silo was newly added in AtlantECO-BASE2.

A list of all data products can be found in **Table A 4.8**.

4.9 AtlantECO-ELSE: Other data sets with data-type specific formatting (D2.1; UU; GENOSCOPE; UNantes; NIOZ)

We further collected a range of other derived data products that cannot easily be converted into the template long-table format due to their underlying structure and data types. These data sets are not or only partly funded by AtlantECO and will be served to the scientific community as service products. These data sets will be recorded as links to publicly available data repositories.

4.9.1 Connectivity data from Manral et al. (2022)

The connectivity dataset is generated from 120 Lagrangian simulations of virtual particles for 30 days across the Atlantic Ocean at different depths using the [GLOB16 ocean model data](#) provided by CMCC. The connectivity between all the grid cells in the Atlantic Ocean region is represented in the form of a binary matrix (.npz file). In addition, different statistics of minimum and maximum temperatures experienced by particles connecting grid cells have been exported in matrices (.npz files), similar to the connectivity matrices. We also performed sensitivity analysis for grid cell resolution and number of particles using surface simulations. This dataset can be used to produce passive or thermally constrained connectivity maps between any set of locations within the Atlantic region.

4.9.2 Further metagenomic resources from Tara Oceans distributed via GENOSCOPE

This submission consists of a large range of analysis products based on genomic and transcriptomic information from the stations of the Tara Oceans expedition, as processed at GENOSCOPE (www.genoscope.cns.fr/tara), and documented in the related publications (Delmont et al. 2022a, 2022b, Vorobev et al. 2018, Carradec et al. 2020, Seeleuthner et al., 2018). Eukaryotic metagenomes have been assembled into metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) and added to a collection of genomes obtained from individual cells (SAGs), giving a total of 683 genomes. This collection covers a large range of the eukaryote radiation. Bacterial and archeal metagenome data (MAGs) contains 1888 curated MAGs, including 48 curated diazotroph MAGs. All these MAGs, eukaryotes and prokaryotes, have been manually curated using the Anvio platform (<https://anvio.org/> ref: doi.org/10.1038/s41564-020-00834-3). Positions of genes were predicted on all these genomes. MATOU is a collection of assembled sequences of transcribed mRNA named unigene sequences. Different annotations have been computed (taxonomic affiliations, protein domain identification; Carradec et al. 2020). MGT is a collection of sequences obtained through a clustering of the MATOU dataset. Therefore, each MGT corresponds to a partial collection of expressed genes, likely corresponding to the same species (Vorobev et al. 2018).

4.9.3 Community networks from Chaffron et al. (2021)

This submission contains a global ocean cross-domain plankton co-occurrence network—the community interactome based on taxonomically annotated OTUs from 115 stations from the Tara Oceans expeditions (2009–2013), covering several organismal size fractions and all major oceanic provinces, with depths corresponding to the surface ocean and the deep chlorophyll maximum only. Co-occurrence graphs were derived from the integration of organismal abundances from two prokaryote-enriched size fractions and four eukaryote size fractions. For prokaryotes, taxonomic profiling was performed using the 16S ribosomal gene fragments in Illumina-sequenced metagenomes and the SILVA database (Sunagawa et al. 2015) for referencing. For eukaryotes, OTUs were derived based on 18S rRNA gene V9 amplicons clustered with the

Swarm version 2.1.1 (De Vargas et al. 2015) and taxonomically and functionally annotated by global pairwise alignment against an updated version (available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3768951>) of the PR2_V9 reference database. On the basis of these taxonomic affiliations, we classified all taxa into Marine Plankton Groups as in (de Vargas et al. 2015). Local graphs were computed for each sampling station and related to environmental predictor variables. The graph inference was performed using FW v0.13.1 using default parameters (Chaffron et al. 2021).

The resulting integrated species association network [referred to as the Global Ocean Plankton Interactome (GPI)] counts a total of 20,810 nodes corresponding to operational taxonomic units (OTUs) and 86,026 edges corresponding to potential biotic interactions. In comparison to a previous plankton interactome generated from Tara Oceans data (Lima-Mendez et al. 2015), the GPI doubled the number of recovered known interactions from the literature. A vast majority of positive associations (98.5%) were predicted, likely underlying a prevalent role for biotic interactions in shaping marine plankton communities (Lima-Mendez et al. 2015). Using a deterministic eigenvector-based network community detection algorithm (Newman, 2006), five communities emerged from the GPI, which were enriched in OTUs assigned to specific biomes, and displayed distinct predicted biotic associations. Through comparison of community abundance profiles, these five communities were preferentially observed in specific biomes as defined by Longhurst's primary biome partitioning (Polar, Westerlies and Trades biomes) (Longhurst, 2010).

4.9.4 Viral oceanography database from Xie et al. (2021) (Service dataset)

This service dataset is a reformatted alternative version of the original dataset from Xie et al. (2021) (not funded by AtlantECO). It is distributed within the AtlantECO project as a service dataset for co-analysis with other datasets from AtlantECO. This version follows the Darwin Core standard vocabulary (DwC) and the table is described in the associated README file. It contains 10,931 georeferenced records of viral abundance (VA) and 727 records of viral production (VP) in global marine environments. It includes measurements of viral and microbial parameters as well as associated oceanographic metadata. The dataset comprises viral particle counts and production rates in coastal and open-ocean waters, from surface to deep-sea layers, and spans various ocean basins including the Atlantic, Pacific, Indian, and Arctic Oceans, as well as the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas.

The dataset was obtained using multiple sampling techniques and detection methods, including transmission electron microscopy (TEM), epifluorescence microscopy (EFM), and flow cytometry (FCM) for VA; and several methodological approaches for VP such as virus reduction approach (VRA), radioactive incorporation (RIA), and frequency-of-infected-cells based estimation (FPB). It also includes auxiliary data like bacterial and phytoplankton abundances, prokaryotic productivity, nutrient concentrations, and environmental parameters (e.g., temperature, salinity, oxygen).

The original dataset is available here: <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.915758> and the list of references here: https://store.pangaea.de/Publications/Xie_et al-2020/References_for_GVOD.txt.

A list of all data products can be found in **Tables A 4.9.1, A 4.9.2, A 4.9.3 and A 4.9.4.**

AtlantECO-CMIP6 (see also AtlantECO-MAPS): Initial AtlantECO compilation of regridded CMIP6 model data for the extrapolation of biological data to different future climates (task 2.3; D2.2; lead: ETHZ/CEA/UBern)

An initial compilation of regridded future projections for selected CMIP6 models, variables and future scenarios can be found under: <https://data.up.ethz.ch/shared/AtlantECO/AtlantECO-CMIP6/>

Models: GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR,

Scenarios: historical, piControl, SSP126, SSP245

Time period: 1850-2014 (historical), 2015 - 2100 (future projections)

Variables: intpn2, intpp, mlotst, no3, o2, ph, phyc, so, spco2, thetao, tos, zooc, zos

Grid: regular degree grid; 360 (lon)x180 (lat) x 12 (months), with variable-specific depth resolution (surface versus full water column)

For further information about variables, grids, simulation set-ups, please consult the CMIP6 website (<https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phase-6-cmip6/>) as well as Eyring et al., (2016) for simulation design and naming conventions.

5 Conclusion

AtlantECO-BASE provides an impressive valuable knowledge base of the marine (micro)biome across taxonomic groups, data streams and all five data silos considered in this project. All data is provided in a consistent file formatting with standardized metadata and readme files. This makes the data unique in its usability and shareability with the science community and international data repositories, and it has been made available to the project partners and the general public using FAIR publishing principles. Here, we compiled more than 50 million global data points across a wide range of taxonomic groups and biological and environmental tracers ranging from enzymes used in bioprospecting applications to carbon flux observations and microplastics concentration, which can form the foundation for a comprehensive assessment of Atlantic ocean ecosystem structure and function, as well as ecosystem health. Many scientific projects exploring and discovering patterns in these data sets have been started, both within and beyond the project, and results have fed into AtlantECO-MAPS (D2.5) and will feed into D2.7. The data has already been partly shared with sister EU HORIZON projects BlueCloud2026 and BiOcean5D, among others, and is likely to form the foundation of many a collaborative study in the future.

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7 Appendix

Table A 4.3.1 Traditional presence-absence data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields (AtlantECO-MAPS); M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request; c: confidential); y:yes, n:no, o:ongoing/preliminary results available, d:derived fields only.

Taxon/Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Phytoplankton species occurrences	PhytoBase (v1) (presence-absence; no.obs: 1,360,621)	BASE/v1_legacy/AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_phytoplankton_species_occurrences_PhytoBasev1_20200313.csv Monthly modelled phytoplankton species richness (from Righetti et al. 2019): MAPS/Phytoplankton_diversity_Righetti_et_al_2019/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome_traditional_phytoplankton_richness_Righetti_et_al_2019_aau6253_data_file_s1.nc Readme: see corresponding journal articles and supplementary material	Presence-absence observations for 1,704 species	y	d	y	n	n	Contact: Meike Vogt (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch) Righetti et al., 2020; doi:10.5194/essd-12-907-2020 Righetti et al., 2019; doi: 10.1126/sciadv.aau6253	10.1594/PANGAEA.904397	p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Zoo-plankton species occurrences	ZooBase (v1) (no. obs: 1,365,232)	BASE/v1_legacy/AtlantECO-BASE-v1_microbiome_traditional_zooplankton_species_occurrences_ZooBasev1_20210714.csv Species richness for 14 functional groups: MAPS/Groups_species_richness_Benedetti_et_al_2021/ Monthly species habitat suitabilities for phyto- and zooplankton species included in Benedetti et al. 2021: MAPS/Species_habitat_suitability_Benedetti_et_al_2021/phytoplankton/ MAPS/Species_habitat_suitability_Benedetti_et_al_2021/zooplankton/ Readme: see corresponding journal article and supplementary material	Presence-absence observations for 3,371 species	y	d	y	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Benedetti et al., 2021; doi:10.1038/s41467-021-25385-x	10.5281/zenodo.5101518 10.5281/zenodo.5101349	p
Updated PhytoBase	PhytoBasev2 (no. obs: 5,167,282)	BASE/traditional_presence_absence/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_presence_absence_PhytoBase_v2.csv	Presence-absence observations for 1,691 species	y	n	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)	-	p
Updated ZooBase	ZooBasev2 (no. obs: 16,662,867)	BASE/traditional_presence_absence/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_presence_absence_ZooBase_v2.csv	Presence-absence observations for 4,072 species	y	n	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)	-	p

Table A 4.3.2 Traditional abundance and biomass data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields (AtlantECO-MAPS); M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available

Taxon/Type	Description (name; no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Amphipoda	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Amphipods (no obs.: 1,449,666)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Amphipoda.csv Carbon conversion tables per taxonomic unit: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Amphipoda_ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Amphipoda_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p
Appendicularia	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Appendicularia (no obs.: 218,159)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Appendicularia.csv Carbon conversion tables per taxonomic unit: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Appendicularia_ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Appendicularia_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p
Bacillariophyta	MAREDAT diatoms (LeBlanc et al. 2012) (reformatted; no obs: 91,704)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_SERVICE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Diatoms_MAREDAT_Leblanc_et_al_2012.csv Gridded biomass data (AtlantECO-GRID; as originally provided in MAREDAT on pangaea.de): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Diatoms_MarEDat20120716Diatoms.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	o	n	n	Contact: Meike Vogt (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch) Leblanc et al., 2012; doi:10.5194/essd-4-149-2012	10.1594/PANGAEA.777384	p

Taxon/ Type	Description (name; no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
		Readme: see corresponding journal article									
Chaetognatha	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Chaetognatha (no obs.: 383,151)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Chaetognatha.csv Carbon conversion tables per taxonomic unit: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Chaetognatha_ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Chaetognatha_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p
Coccolithophores	MAREDAT coccolithophores (O'Brien/Peloquin et al. 2012) (reformatted; no obs. 58,109)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_SERVICE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Coccolithophores_MAREDAT_O'Brien_et_al_2013.csv Gridded biomass data (AtlantECO-GRID; as originally provided in MAREDAT on pangaea.de): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Coccolithophores_MarEDat20120620Coccolithophores.nc Readme: see corresponding journal article	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	o	n	n	Contact: Meike Vogt (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch) O'Brien et al., 2013; doi:10.5194/essd-5-259-2013	10.1594/PANGAEA.785092	p
Copepoda	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Copepoda (no obs.: 9,080,989)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Copepoda.csv Carbon conversion per taxonomic unit: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Copepoda_ind_carbon_value.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID):	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (name; no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
		GRID/AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome_traditional_Copepoda_abund+biomass_20220930.nc									
Dinoflagellata	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Dinoflagellata (no obs.: 4,339,695)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Dinoflagellates.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): Work in progress	Abundances (cells.m-3 & cells.L-1) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3 and µgC.L-1)	y	o	o	n	n	Contact: Meike Vogt (meike.vogt@env.ethz.ch) N. Chénier, in prep.		p
Euphausiacea	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Euphausiacea (no obs.: 1,071,450)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Euphausiacea.csv Carbon conversion per taxonomic unit: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Euphausiacea.ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Euphausiacea_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p
Foraminifera	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Foraminifera (no obs.: 1,026,933)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Foraminifera.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Foraminifera_abund+biomass_20221126.nc Extrapolated data: MAPS/Zooplankton_Calcifier_biomass_Knechtetal.2023/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome_traditional_Foraminifera_extrapolated_model_outputs_20221126.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	o	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Knecht et al., submitted; doi:10.2254/essoar.167283650.05543210/v1	10.1594/PANGAEA.957258	p
Jellyfish	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Jellyfish.csv	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (name; no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	for Jellyfish (Cnidaria+Ctenophora ; no obs.: 590,371)	Carbon conversion table per taxonomic group: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Jellyfish_ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Jellyfish_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	concentrations (mgC.m-3)						(fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		
Ostracoda	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Ostracoda (no obs.: 133,533)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Ostracoda.csv Carbon conversion tables per taxonomic group: BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Ostracoda_ind_carbon_values.xlsx Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Ostracoda_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch)		p
Pteropoda	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Pteropoda (no obs.: 841,239)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Pteropoda.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditional_Pteropoda_abund+biomass_20220714.nc Extrapolated data: MAPS/Zooplankton Calcifier biomass Knecht et al 2023/ AtlantECO-MAPS-v1_microbiome_traditional_Pteropoda_extrapolated_model_outputs_20220714.nc	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass concentrations (mgC.m-3)	y	y	o	y	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Knecht et al., submitted; doi:10.2254/essoar.167283650.05543210/v1	10.1594/PANGAEA.957258	p
Thaliacea	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantECO_BASE_traditional_abundance_biomass_Thaliacea.csv	Abundances (ind.m-3) converted to biomass	y	y	o	y	n	Contact: Corentin Clerc	Clerc et al. 2023 (10.5194/bg-20-869-2023)	p

Taxon/ Type	Description (name; no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Data contact & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	for Thaliacea (no obs.: 447,920)	Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_traditiona l_Thaliacea_abund+biomass_20220930.nc	concentrations (mg.C.m-3)						(corentin.clerc@usys.e thz.ch; cclerc@lmd.ipsl.fr) Paper: Clerc et al., 2023; 10.5194/bg-20-869-20 23	Data supplement: <a href="https://zenodo.org/record/7573432#.Y9ebhu
zMIZO">https://zenodo.org/record/7573432#.Y9ebhu zMIZO	
Diazotrophs	Global compilation of field observations of abundances/biomass for Diazotrophs (no obs.: 294,060)	BASE/traditional_abundance_biomass/AtlantEC O_BASE_traditional_and_omics_Diazotrophs.cs v Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/Diazotroph_quantitative_fields_gridded.20 22/ Gridded fields contain Mean/Median/Stdev/Min and Max of the diazotroph abundances (trichome_counts_perVolume, cell_counts_perVolume and nifH_gene_counts_perVolume). netCDF file also contains one variable indicating the number of observations.	Abundances (trichomes.m-3 & m-2, cells..L-1 & cm-2 & m-2 & m-3, nifH.m-3 & L-1 & m-2) converted to biomass concentrations (mg.C.m-3 & mg.C.m-2)	y	y	o	y	n	Contact: Dominic Eriksson (dominic.eriksson@us ys.ethz.ch)		p

Table A 4.4 Optical imaging data sets gathered (quality controlled images taken by different imaging instruments):

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available; d: derived fields only

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L	
Images (ECOTAXA):												
Tara Oceans	Tara confocal microscopy (e-HFCM), Flowcam, Zooscan and UVP data; Ecotaxa	<p>images recorded in Ecotaxa:</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/3365 (eHFCM >5µm 336,655 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/2274 (eHFCM >20µm 1,235,640 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/326 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/327 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/328 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/329 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/330</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/331 (Flowcam 744,409 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/378 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/377 (Zooscan - WP2 net 399,204 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/395 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/398 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/397 (Zooscan - Bongo net 326,896 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/412 (Zooscan - Regent net 126,389 images)</p> <p>https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/579 (LVP 776,497 images)</p>	images taxonomic identification morphological measurements	with and	y	n	n	n	n	Contact person: Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr)		p
Tara Pacific	Tara Pacific Flowcam and Zooscan data; Ecotaxa;	<p>images recorded in Ecotaxa:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.17882/102694</p>	images taxonomic identification	with and	r	n	n	n	n	Contact person: Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr)	Mériguet et al 2025 https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2761-2025	p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	published with Mériguet et al 2025 https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2761-2025	https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11370 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11369 https://doi.org/10.17882/102697 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11353 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11341 (Flowcam 2,528,719 images) https://doi.org/10.17882/102537 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/1345 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/1344 https://doi.org/10.17882/102336 https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/11292 (Zooscan 375,732 images)	morphological measurements								
Mission Microbiomes	Tara Microbiome Flowcam/Planktoscope /P2/net/UVP data; Ecotaxa Ongoing work of analysis (displayed here by legs, only images validated by taxonomic expert visible)	images recorded on Ecotaxa: https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/3891 (Flowcam 88,465 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/3892 (Flowcam 66,243 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4343 (Planktoscope 115,119 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4356 (P2/miniHSN 98,260 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4362 (P2/miniHSN 13,176 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4363 (P2/deckNet 17,203 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/5254 (LVP 298,478 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/4559 (Flowcam Net 20 518,671 images) https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/6058	images with taxonomic identification and morphological measurements	r	n	n	n	n	Contact person: Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr)		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
		(Flowcam Net 20 43,053 images)									
JERICO	LVP data	images recorded on Ecotaxa https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/prj/578 (74,769 images)		y	n	n	n	n	Contact person: Lars Stemmann (lars.stemmann@imev-mer.fr)		p

Table A 4.4.1 Synthesis data sets from optical imaging gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available; d: derived fields only

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	DissL
Synthesis products:											
Vertical profiles of particles size and biovolume distribution SERVICE dataset	Particle size distribution data collected during multiple cruises globally with several regularly intercalibrated Underwater Vision Profilers, Version 5 (UVP5) (no. obs: 2,083,352 across 29 particles size classes)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_SERV/CE_UVP5_particle_abundance_biovolume_kiko_et_al_2022.csv	Particles concentrations and biovolume (mm3.l-1) across 29 size classes (ranging from 0.0403 mm to > 26 mm)	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr) ; Lionel Guidi (lionel.guidi@imev-mer.fr) Kiko et al., 2022; doi:10.5194/essd-14-4315-2022	Kiko et al. (2021) https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.924375	p
Broad zooplankton clades and Copepod families SERVICE dataset	Zooscan Tara Oceans data: WP2, Bongo and Régent nets (no. obs = 15,908)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_SERV/CE_zooplankton_abundance_biomass_Brandao_et_al_2021.csv	Abundances (concentrations) of large zooplankton groups and copepod families	y	n	n	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Brandao et al., 2021; doi:10.1038/s41598-021-94615-5	Brandão et al. (2021) https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-94615-5 doi: https://doi.org/10.17632/mwvjwccgyh.1	p
Broad zooplankton clades and Copepod families SERVICE dataset	Zooscan Tara Oceans data: WP2, Multinet (no. obs = 5,415)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_SERV/CE_protists_zooplankton_abundance_biomass_Soviadan_et_al_2022.csv	Abundances (concentrations) and biomass of zooplankton groups	y	n	n	n	n	Contact: Fabio Benedetti (fabio.benedetti@usys.ethz.ch) Soviadan et al., 2022; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2021.102717 .	Soviadan et al. (2022) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocan.2021.102717	p
Broad zooplankton clades (most precise)	Brazilian UVP: casts performed at 37 sampling stations	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_UVP5_zooplankton_Brazil_abundance_biomass.csv	Abundance, biovolume and zooplankton biomass, images	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Gleice de Souza Santos (gleicesantos@usp.br),		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	DissL
taxonomic resolution allowed by the LVP5)	around the Vitória Trindade Seamount Chain (Brazil), during “Ilhas” cruise. (no. obs = 1,347)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_UV_P5_zooplankton_Brazil_biovolume_biomass.csv	obtained in the casts can be accessed in EcoTaxa platform (Project “Uvp5_sn200_ilhas_2017_filtered_vignettes”).						Rubens Mendes Lopes (rubens@usp.br)		
Broad plankton clades	(no. obs = 257,091)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_mesoplankton_biomass.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr)	Lombard et al. (2024) https://zenodo.org/records/10478781	p
Broad plankton clades	(no. obs = 2,335,056)	BASE/imaging_synthesis/AtlantECO_BASE_plankton_plastic_abundances.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Fabien Lombard (fabien.lombard@imev-mer.fr)	Mériguet et al. (2024) https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2024-507 Raw dataset: FlowCam Tara Pacific Deck Net 20 microns: https://doi.org/10.17882/102697 FlowCam Tara Pacific Bongo Net 20 microns: https://doi.org/10.17882/102694 ZooScan Tara Pacific High-Speed Net 330 microns: https://doi.org/10.17882/102336 ZooScan Tara Pacific Manta Net 330 microns: https://doi.org/10.17882/102537	p

Table A 4.5 Molecular data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
MGNify Superstudy	AtlantECO Superstudy, Metagenomes (no. obs = 835)	Online source: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/super-studies/atlanteco	Metagenomes globally distributed, covering different plankton size fractions and water column depths	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com)		p
Metagenomes: Functional diversity - planktonic communities 0.2-3 µm size fraction	AtlantECO Metagenomic database (no. obs = 451)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_prokaryotes_functional_diversity.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO-GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_MetaG_FunctionalDiversity_02-3um_202211121.nc	Functional diversity based on KEGG orthologs (KOs)	y	y	n	y	o	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com)		u
Metagenomes: Nitrogen metabolisms - planktonic communities 0.2-3 µm size fraction	AtlantECO Metagenomic database (no. obs = 8,118)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_KO_nitrogen_path_abundance.csv	Counts of 18 genes based on KEGG orthologs (KOs) representative of Nitrogen metabolism	y	o	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com)		p
Amplicon 16S rRNA Database	AtlantECO Amplicon database (no. obs = 169,639)	BASE/omics_16S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_16S_prokaryote.csv	Tara Oceans and Malaspina 16S Amplicon database (counts of ASVs per sampling stations).	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br)		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
									Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		
Amplicon 18S rRNA V9 region Database	AtlantECO Amplicon database (no. obs = 477,939)	BASE/omics_18S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_18S_eukaryotes.csv	Tara Oceans and Malaspina 18S V9 region Amplicon databases (counts if ASVs per sampling station).	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p
Ocean Prokaryotic Diversity	AtlantECO Amplicon 16S database (no. obs = 428)	BASE/omics_16S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_16S_prokaryote_Shannon_diversity.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_AmpSeq16S-Pk_ShannonDiversityProkaryotes_2023_0208.nc	Shannon diversity index of Prokaryotes based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p
Ocean Autotrophic Prokaryotes Abundance	AtlantECO Amplicon 16S database (no. obs = 428)	BASE/omics_16S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_16S_autotrophic_prokaryotes_abundance.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_AmpSeq16S-Pk_AutotrophicProkaryotesAbundance_20230208.nc	Autotrophic Prokaryotes Abundance based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p
Ocean Heterotrophic Prokaryotes Abundance	AtlantECO Amplicon 16S database (no. obs = 428)	BASE/omics_16S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_16S_heterotrophic_prokaryotes_abundance.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO/GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_AmpSeq16S-Pk_HeterotrophicProkaryotesAbundance_20230208.nc	Heterotrophic Prokaryotes Abundance based on 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Ocean Eukaryotic Diversity	AtlantECO Amplicon 18S V9 database (no. obs = 1,405)	BASE/omics_18S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_18S_eukaryotes_Shannon_diversity.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO-GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_AmpSeq18S-Pk_ShannonDiversityEukaryotes_20230208.nc	Shannon diversity index of Eukaryotes based on 18S rRNA gene V9 region amplicon sequencing	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p
Ocean Eukaryotic Abundance	AtlantECO Amplicon 18S V9 database (no. obs = 1,405)	BASE/omics_18S/AtlantECO_BASE_AmpSeq_18S_eukaryotes_abundance.csv Gridded data (AtlantECO-GRID): GRID/AtlantECO-GRID-v1_microbiome_omics_AmpSeq18S-Pk_EukaryoticAbundance_20230208.nc	Abundance of Eukaryotes based on 18S rRNA gene V9 region amplicon sequencing	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Clara Arboleda-Baena (claraarboledab@gmail.com)		p
Ocean Carbon Substrate Usage	AtlantECO MAGSubs database (no. obs = 2,235)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_CAZymes_richness.csv	Number of CAZyme protein families found per MAG	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Célio Dias Santos Júnior (celio.diasjunior@gmail.com)		u
Ocean Carbon Substrate Usage	AtlantECO MAGSubs database (no. obs = 2,235)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_predicted_carbon_substrates_per_MAGs.csv	Number of Predicted Carbon Substrates per MAG	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Hugo Sarmiento (hsarmiento@ufscar.br) Célio Dias Santos Júnior		u

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
									(celio.diasjunior@gmail.com)		
Core Operational Protein Unit (OPUs) Distribution Database	(no. obs = 27,580)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_OPUs_presence_absence.csv	Presence/absence of Core Operational Protein Units (OPUs)	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com) Hugo Sarmiento (hugo.sarmiento@gmail.com)		u
Ocean Microbial Taxonomic Diversity and Richness (mOTUs)	(no. obs = 3,630)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_mOTUs_functional_richness_and_diversity.csv	Functional Diversity and Richness based on KEEG orthologs (KOs)	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com) Hugo Sarmiento (hugo.sarmiento@gmail.com)		u
Ocean Microbial Functional Diversity and Richness	(no. obs = 1,532))	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_functional_richness_and_diversity.csv	Functional Diversity and Richness based on KEEG orthologs (KOs)	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Paula Huber (mariapaulahuber@gmail.com) Hugo Sarmiento (hugo.sarmiento@gmail.com)		u
DNA concentration in seawater Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 599)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_DNA_concentration_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv	Mass of DNA per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
DNA concentration in seawater Tara Pacific Ocean-Atmosphere stations	(no. obs = 410)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_DNA_concentration_Tara_pacific.csv	Mass of DNA per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Cell abundance in seawater of eukaryotic SMAGs across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 112,615)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_eukaryotic_SMAGs_cell_abundance_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv	Cell abundance per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
DNA concentration in seawater of eukaryotic SMAGs across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 360,065)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_eukaryotic_SMAGs_dna_concentration_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv	Mass of DNA per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
Cell abundance in seawater of prokaryotic SMAGs across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 257,550)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_prokaryotic_SMAGs_cell_abundance_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv	Cell abundance per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
DNA concentration in seawater of prokaryotic SMAGs across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 409,800)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_prokaryotic_SMAGs_dna_concentration_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv	Mass of DNA per water volume	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
Cell abundance of phytoplankton taxa based on psbO reference sequences across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples	(no. obs = 146,944)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_psbO_gene_cell_abundance_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
Cell abundance of psbO-based phytoplankton	(no. obs = 4,823)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_psbO_lineage_cell_abundance_Tara_oceans_polar_circle.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville		u

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
lineages across Tara Oceans and Polar Circle surface samples									(mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		
Cell abundance of phytoplankton taxa based on psbO reference sequences across Tara Pacific Ocean-Atmosphere (OA) samples	(no. obs = 45,502)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_psbO_gene_dna_concentration_Tara_pacific.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
Cell abundance of psbO-based phytoplankton lineages across Tara Pacific Ocean-Atmosphere samples	(no. obs = 1,727)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_psbO_lineage_dna_concentration_Tara_pacific.csv		y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Margaux Crédeville (mcredevi@genoscope.cns.fr) Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.cns.fr)		u
Alpha diversity metrics (richness, Shannon, Chao1) computed from metagenomic taxonomic profiles (mOTU-level)	(no. obs = 2,652,723)	BASE/omics_metagenomes/AtlantECO_BASE_prokaryotes_diversity.csv	Species richness, Shannon, Chao1	y	n	n	y	n	Dominic Eriksson (deriksson@ethz.ch)		u

Table A 4.5.1 Plastisphere data sets with data-type specific formatting gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO’s GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Plastisphere Amplicon 16S rRNA Database	AtlantECO Amplicon database (no. obs = 357)	AtlantECO-Base-v1_microbiome_genomic_GenD B-AmpSeq16S-Plastisphere-database_V1.0.csv	Plastisphere Amplicon 16S rRNA Database; georeference database + sapling metadata & env. variables	y	o	n	o	n	Contact person: Linda Amaral-Zettler (linda.amaral-zettler@nioz.nl)	https://doi.org/10.1890/150017	p

Table A 4.6 Carbon flux data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
POC fluxes based on Thorium-234 deficits and sediment traps	Carbon flux rate measured by sediment traps and Thorium (Th-234) disequilibria. Data depth range: 5 - 5847 m. 15,425 obs.	BASE/carbon_fluxes_234Th_sediment_traps/AtlantECO_BASE_carbon_fluxes_234Th_sediment_traps.csv	MgC.m-2.day-1	y	y	n	y	n	Contact person: Florian Ricour (Florian.Ricour@uliege.be) Ricour et al, PhD thesis		p
Particle size distribution based on UVP imaging data	1,864999 obs. taken from depth range of 2.5 to 6017.5 m.	BASE/carbon_fluxes_UVP_particle_sizes/AtlantECO_BASE_size_spectra_UVP5.csv	27 size ranges (from ESD: 0.0508-0.064mm to 20.6-26 mm) of particle concentration fractions	y	n	n	y	n	Contact person: Florian Ricour (Florian.Ricour@uliege.be) Ricour et al, PhD thesis	10.1594/PANGAEA.924375	p
Carbon fluxes based on particle size distribution based on UVP imaging data derived from Guidi et al., 2008	Information (number of observations per grid cell) are provided in the NetCDF	AtlantECO-BASE-v1_carbon-flux_UVP5_20230301.nc	MgC.m-2.day-1	n	y	n	n	n	Contact person: Lionel Guidi and Florian Ricour (lionel.guidi@imev-mer.fr , florian.ricour@uliege.be)		p

Table A 4.7 Microplastics data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	DissL
Microplastics	(no. obs = 13,159)	BASE/microplastics/AtlantECO_BASE_microplastics.csv	Concentration of floating plastics	y	y	n	y	n	Contact: Erik Van Sebille (e.vansebille@uu.nl) Schmiz et al. MSc thesis		p

Table A 4.8 Bioprospecting data sets gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/Type	Description (no. obs)	Filename(s)	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	DissL
Enzymes	This data submission contains detection of enzyme of interest in the AtlantECO Mgnify superstudy (no. obs = 4,011).	BASE/bioprospecting/AtlantECO_BASE_enzymes_candidates.csv	Enzyme family name	y	n	n	y	n	Contact: Jonathan Elias Holme (jonathan.holme@sintef.no) Giang-Son Nguyen (giangson.nguyen@sintef.no)		p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	<p>maximum temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maximum of minimum/maximum temperatures• Average of minimum/maximum temperatures <p>Link to the data repository:</p> <p>https://public.yoda.uu.nl/science/UU01/HVXLBO.html</p>										

Table A 4.9.2 AtlantECO-ELSE: Omics data sets with data-type specific formatting gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Eukaryotic MAGs from Delmont et al (2022a)	<p>This data submission consists of the analysis of eukaryotic Tara Oceans (meta)genomes, including:</p> <p>11raw metagenomic co-assemblies, the FASTA files for 713 MAGs and SAGs, the \$10 million protein-coding sequences (nucleotides, amino acids and gff format), and the curated DNA-dependent RNA polymerase genes (MAGs and SAGs and METdb transcriptions)</p> <p>Link to resources:</p> <p>https://www.genoscope.cns.fr/tara/</p> <p>Data subheader:</p> <p>Tara Oceans Eukaryotic Genomes (the "SMAGs")</p>	multiple zip archives containing files with multiple file formats	<p>SMAGs:</p> <p>curated SMAGs and single cell genomes</p> <p>metagenomic co-assemblies</p> <p>curated DNA-dependent RNA polymerase</p>	n	n	y	y	n	<p>Contact: Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.fr)</p> <p>Related papers: Delmont et al. 2022a https://www.cell.com/cell-genomics/pdf/S2666-979X(22)00047-7.pdf</p>	n	p

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Bacterial MAGs including 48 Diazotroph MAGs from Delmont et al., 2022b	<p>This data submission consists of resources related to the analysis of Tara Oceans (meta)genomic information, including metagenomic co-assemblies, FASTA files, and a diazotroph genomic database.</p> <p>Link to resources: https://www.genoscope.cns.fr/tara/</p> <p>Data subheader: Tara Oceans Bacterial and Archaeal Genomes (the "BAC_ARC_MAGs")</p> <p>Diazotrophs: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Marine_diazotrophs/14248283</p>	multiple zip archives containing files with multiple file formats	<p>BAC_ARC_MAGs:</p> <p>1888 curated MAGs including 48 curated diazotroph MAGs</p>	n	n	n	y	n	<p>Contact: Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.fr)</p> <p>Related papers: Delmont et al. 2022b https://www.nature.com/articles/s41396-021-01135-1 https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Marine_diazotrophs/14248283</p>	n	P
Further collection of Genoscope Tara resources	<p>A large collection of genomic resources based on the analysis of Tara Oceans data:</p> <p>https://www.genoscope.cns.fr/tara/</p> <p>Data subheaders:</p>	multiple zip archives containing files with multiple file formats	<p>MGT: Metagenome-based Transcriptome</p> <p>MATOU:</p> <p>unigene sequences</p> <p>taxonomic affiliations</p>	n	n	n	n	n	<p>Contact: Olivier Jaillon (ojaillon@genoscope.fr)</p> <p>Related papers: MGT: Vorobev et al. 2020</p>	n	P

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
	MetaGenomic Transcriptomes (MGT) Tara Oceans Eukaryote Gene Catalog (the "MATOU") Single-cell genomes		protein domain identification metagenomic occurrences metatranscriptomic occurrences unigenes cluster compositions and properties Single-cell genomics: MAST-3 and MAST-4 clades Chrysophyte clades						MATOU: Carradec et al. 2020 Single-cell genomes: Seeleuthner et al. 2018		

Table A 4.9.3 AtlantECO-ELSE: Interactome data sets with data-type specific formatting gathered:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 01-23); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Plankton interactome from Chaffron et al., 2021	<p>This data submission contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OTUs abundance matrices used for inferring the GPI: https://uncloud.univ-nantes.fr/index.php/s/yePQAsTxeFW7Sw - The GPI interactome as a graphML file: https://uncloud.univ-nantes.fr/index.php/s/G6ybiG8pHsikYij - The GPI interactome, merged at the OTU level, as a graphML file: https://uncloud.univ-nantes.fr/index.php/s/tSL3Xks6yRPZ5o4 	<p>zip archives with abundance matrices and graphML files</p> <p>Example file name: GPI.graphml.zip</p>	<p>OTU abundance matrices,</p> <p>GPI interactome graphs (vertices and edges)</p>	n	n	n	n	n	<p>Contact: Samuel Chaffron (samuel.chaffron@univ-nantes.fr)</p> <p>Related papers:</p> <p>Chaffron et al. 2021 https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.abg1921</p> <p>(see Supplementary materials)</p>	10.1126/sciadv.abg1921_SOM	p

Table A 4.9.4 AtlantECO-ELSE: Viral oceanography data set:

Vars: variables included; R: raw data; G: gridded data; E: extrapolated fields; M: readme; N: published on AtlantECO's GeoNode (status: 04-25); DissL: Dissemination Level (p: public, u: upon request); y: yes; n: no; o: ongoing work/preliminary results available, d: derived fields only.

Taxon/ Type	Description (no. obs) and links to public data repository	Filename(s) and formats	Vars	R	G	E	M	N	Contact person & Related reference/s	Data doi	Diss L
Global viral oceanography database from Xie et al., 2021 SERVICE dataset	This data submission contains records of viral production and viral abundance (no. obs = 10,963).	BASE/else/AtlantECO_BASE_SERVICE_viral_oceanography_Xie_et_al_2021.csv ASE_viruses.csv	Virus and prokaryote abundance	y	n	n	y	n	Contact: Related papers: Xie et al., 2021 https://essd.copernicus.org/articles/13/1251/2021/	10.1594/PANGAEA.915758	p